

The Contribution of Family Socio-Economic Status on School Dropout in Public Secondary Schools of Rwanda

¹Nsengimana Charles, ²Mukurira Olivier

^{1,2}Mount Kenya University, Rwanda

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Abstract: The study entitled, “the contribution of family socio-economic status on school dropout in public secondary schools of Rwanda”. The researcher identified family socio-economic status of families of the students of secondary schools of Nyarugenge District-Rwanda; to examine the level of students’ dropout rate in secondary schools of Nyarugenge District-Rwanda; ascertained the relationship between family socio-economic status and dropout rate in secondary schools of Nyarugenge District-Rwanda. The researcher adopted the descriptive survey design because the study seeks to gain insight or perception into a phenomenon as a way of providing basic information in an area of study. The study sample size was comprised 250 in total including 50 teachers, 1 head teacher, 26 parents and 173 students of 1 secondary school leader in Nyarugenge District. To determine the sample size, the researcher used Yamane formula for sample size determination and the sample size was 250. At each school level, head teacher and parents were purposively sampled, while teachers and students used sampled using simple random sampling. The researcher used the questionnaire and interview to collect data. It was concluded that the family played a big role in the children education. The respondents confirmed that the students dropout due to family unemployment and low income family, and it was confirmed by 12% who answered always and 66% answered sometimes. This implied that both students from low income families were likely to dropout due to lack of basic needs and assistance from their family members. The results showed that the P-value was .01. While the Spearman correlation was -.2. This means that family socio-economic status negatively affects the dropout rate in secondary schools. The researcher recommended that the City of Kigali should strengthen parental mobilization to the involvement in children education. The district of Nyarugenge should grant much training on both students and parents on the causes and consequences of school dropout. The researcher suggested that the educational officials should conduct regular inspections in schools and communities to ensure all children attend schools.

Keywords: Family Words, Socio-economic status, Students’ Dropout, Dropout rate.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Both scientific and empirical evidences argued that family status contributes to the education of children. In fact, parental involvement in education of their children because pertinent in learners learning outcomes owing to effective cooperation between teachers and parents or guardians (Duatscher & Ibe, 2003). Globally, family plays influence to the success of learners in secondary schools. In this vein, whether family care students at school, they will attain the highest level of learning outcomes.

In African countries, educational performance is one of the greatest element in the community. However, in less developed countries, student performance is a crucial in developing personal and communal ability in the community.

Therefore, features represented by family socio economic status in educating their children in making sure that the learners relies on researches and were capable to possess adequate learning outcomes (Chowa, Ansong and Osei-Akolo, 2012).

In Rwanda, a crucial development step to the attainment of education targets. The strategy relied on world secondary school forum. However, poor performance continues to exist in Rwanda. The Government and other stakeholders are involved in establishing the way to enhance academic performance and obtain higher level of profitability. The quality of learning become poor owing to the lack of learning and teaching equipment's, the existence of unconducive environment to execute strategic mechanism and dropout (URT, 2010). In Nyarugenge District, all Secondary schools are owned either by private persons or government or government aided representatives. These schools have been constructed as a consequence of political landscape, lack of relying on fundamental requirements in providing high level of education quality. In this regards, the present research assessed the relationship between socio-economic status and drop out in selected secondary of Nyarugenge District, Rwanda.

1.2 Problem Statement

The greatest impediment in Rwandan education system, and Rwanda in general and Nyarugenge District in particular is the growing problem of school dropout. In fact, most of research on dropout in the City of Kigali, Nyarugenge District, and parental socio-economic status on school dropout rate is not well studied. For instance, a research carried out by Barongo (2007) on dropout in secondary school in Rwanda evidences many causes that lead to school dropout. Therefore, 58.3% of teaching staff members evidenced the poor living conditions and family conflicts could lead to dropout of students.

However, many of the students joined secondary schools at their overage stages others were delinquent while others were taken from streets of Kigali City. Therefore, the researcher wants to assess family socio-economic status on dropout rate in secondary schools of Nyarugenge District in in Rwanda.

1.3 General Objective

This research evaluated family socio-economic status contribution on school dropout rate in secondary schools of Nyarugenge District, Rwanda.

1.4 Specific Objectives

Specifically, the researcher achieved the following specific objectives:

- i. To identify socio-economic status of parents on reduction of school dropout rate in secondary schools of Nyarugenge District-Rwanda.
- ii. To examine the level of students' dropout rate in secondary schools of Nyarugenge District-Rwanda.
- iii. To examine the relationship between family socio-economic status and dropout rate in secondary schools of Nyarugenge District-Rwanda.

1.5 Significance of the Study

The research findings will provide evidences on several causes of dropout in secondary school by focusing on family socio-economic situation as results will reveal the copying strategies to overcome drop out. Results will help to ameliorate education attainment and decrease the level of school dropout rate. The study findings will assist educational practitioners and stakeholders including Head Teachers (HTs), Sector Education Officers (SEOs), District Education Officer (DEOs), and District Director of Education (DDE) to ascertain the growing issue related to school dropout rate and take preventive strategies. This research will give relevant evidenced related to dropout rate for further studies.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 An overview of the family socio-economic status in secondary schools dropout

The family socioeconomic status is normally classified into some dimensions such as family income, family member's level of education, parental occupation. According to Lazer (2002) evidenced that scholars had gathered exciting documents indicating education and emotion complexities that learners from widowed household and step parents. The

study discovered that learners from single mother acquired few years of schooling and have been subjected to dropping out. Descendants from those women were committing crimes and involving in tobacco consumption than descendants to married households.

In addition, low level of revenue from those households experienced high discrepancies in comparison with children who had both mother and father. The effect of single familiness was similar around a wide number of ethical categories. Students from single parents have been facing learning issues. In this regard, 70 percent of students from divorced or separated families were disqualified or postponed from secondary school those existing with biological fathers and mothers. Students with mothers who did not have husbands possess their level of expertise.

According to Mullen (2006) felt that it was assessed that fragmented or destroyed households that could lead to death, divorce or temporal separation may impact drop out in secondary. Students who do not have their fathers contribute to truancy and drop out. Therefore, in Africa, households consider fathers as the pioneer of household socio-economic status.

According to Davidoff (2017) felt that children from higher income families recorded poor performance. This is owing to the role of father in assuming socio-economic responsibility. Most of them recognized poor success and high level of drop out. A study of Olubadewo and Ogwu (2005), 19% of household in America was a step household and 30% of children are living in those families. The study argued that these households were established when separated families established new households.

According to Hyera (2003) established the effect of social cultural norms on drop out of girls in secondary schools in Nyarugenge District in Rwanda. Results evidenced that socio-cultural norms have a different effect on drop out of schools for girls. Girls in secondary schools who desire to drop out for early family creation were impregnate and drop schools.

2.2 The families' education levels and occupation to students' dropout rate

Various studies have been done on the families job lead to a higher of people who drop out. According to Barongo (2007), it was evidenced that students from educated families with good job have been in agriculture, fisheries, small trading activities and these rendered many children to dropping out. However, when fathers or mothers are employed (teaching, nursing, are more likely to perform well in secondary schools. Besides, this they assisted children to reduce the number of children who dropped out. The prevalence of dropping out schools is highly correlated with illiterate, poor education level and poor unemployment for their family members. According to Babyeya (2002), it was demonstrated that absenteeism and dropping out were statistically associated with drop out. The reason behind these dropout were for instance poor parental participation in education activities of their children, poor competency of parents, unemployment, unconducive environment and students absenteeism.

2.3 Family socio-economic status and Students Dropout

According to World Bank report (2001) on Rwanda revealed that dropout occur as the growing issues owing to the fact that most of children did not terminate their studies. Most of researches evidenced that dropout is causes by poor leaving conditions. Moreover, A research done by Remberger (2005) demonstrated that in the United States of America most of students dropped out because of poor living conditions, low capability of families, low level of education, low cost to be find for education.

A research of Croft (2002) carried out in Malawi evidenced that family revenue was pertinent element for educational attainment. This was caused by inability to find expenses allocated to educational activities of their children. The study denoted that those expenses includes costs for studying, school materials and equipment's, uniform, transport and other costs related to children care.

2.4 Empirical Review

Maziku (2013) undertake a research purposed to examine influence of parental socio-economic status on school dropout in basic secondary schools in Tanzania. The author undertook this research in Kahama District using a sample size of five regions. The sampled size was 241 participants include parents or guardians, school principals, teaching staff members, DEO, dropped students and registered one. The study used judgmental sampling techniques, while interview guide, questionnaire and desk review were used to gather information. Results felt that poor living conditions lead to higher rate of drop out. In addition, poor parent educational profile is associated with higher level of dropout. Therefore, of students

who dropped out have been involved in small transition activities like vegetables and fruits, extractive companies, housekeeping, agricultural activities and fetching water. According to the results, the author suggested that public institutions would contribute to the follow up of their children in secondary schools. Moreover, there is a need of more workshop and in service training (Maziku, 2013).

Kapinga (2014), in his study that aimed to examine effect of parental socioeconomic status (SES) on students' academic achievement in secondary school. The study was guided by two specific objectives. These were the way in which family's job; revenue and conducive conditions influence student learning outcome, and the level of parental socio-economic status influence on educating their children are more likely to affect their success. This research was conducted descriptively. Purposively, the researcher selected 60 key participants. This study gathered information using interview guide and group interview and have been analyzed using qualitative method through content analysis. Findings conducted by Drew and Segi (2003), found out that most of learners in secondary schools are from poor living conditions. The research evidenced the existence of significant association between socioeconomic status and educational performance. The study felt that many parents or guardians are not participated in the education activities of their children at school. The research recommended a revision of cost sharing policies and abolition of schools fees and school feeding fees for students from poor living conditions. Finally, more schools must hire counselors to assist learners in reducing school dropout (Drew and Segi. 2003).

Trine and Johan (2015) in their study noted that dropout in young boys and girls were pertinent for suitable living conditions perspective. Generally, acknowledged that parent status has been connected with dropping out. The study aimed to explore and assess influence of social positions and dropout in Denmark. The research adopted structured research instruments (Trine and Johan, 2015).

2.5 Theoretical Framework

The researcher crowned the theoretical framework justified through logically related to family socio-economic status and behavioral and motivation theory.

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs

Theory of Maslow hierarchy the girls and boys in capacity building and how they might be distant, they household. Therefore, when pupils were focused on parent involvement. People were expected to attain their achievement supports persons to meet their expected targets (Malow, 1943). Therefore, behavior would be focused on attainment of expected goals for starting physiology types are for instance accommodation, deity, clothing.

2.6 Conceptual Framework

The following model describes the interrelationship among independent and dependent variable:

Source: Primary source (2022)

Figure 1

The conceptual framework relates the independent variables: family socio-economic status: Family education background, family income, family activities, family life condition and age, and family possibilities to the dependent variables: high dropout level, poor students' academic performance poor students' discipline, irregular attendance to school, learner's delinquency. The researcher also brought in the intervening variables that are government educational policies, school environment, school rules and regulations.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

A research design refers to a blue print adopted to obtain responses. It denotes the management of data collection and analysis procedures (Komp & Tromp, 2006). In this regards, the researcher carried out this study descriptively and comparatively. A descriptive study refers to the process where data are gathered using interview or distributing questionnaire to a sampled population. This kind of design was adopted to gather evidences related to respondents perception, ideas, habits and educational attainment. Furthermore, a comparative research design was adopted to make a comparison or a contrast for analyzing several categories of learners in accordance with socio-economic status to make concluding remarks in order to overcome the growing problem of school dropout.

3.2 Sample Size

Denscombe (2008) argues that a sample would be chosen to represent the target population and give data that may be assessed in scientific way. The author calculated the sample size utilizing Yamane formula. Therefore, based a sample size was 250 respondents and key informants.

Table 1: Target Population and Sample Size

Respondents Group	Target Population	Sample Size
Head Teachers	1	1
Teachers	54	50
Students	545	173
Parents	70	26
Total	670	250

Source: Primary source (2022)

3.3 Sampling Techniques

According to Frankel and Wallen (1990), a sampling technique refers to technique and process that used by the researcher in choosing the representative group from the entire target population. In addition, sampling procure refers to a systematic bleu print for acquiring relevant representative group as sampled population from the entire target one. Therefore, purpose sampling denotes a non-probability sampling technique refers to a non-probability sampling technique judgmentally to select key informants in accordance with persons assumed to be very pertinent in obtained relevant data (Frankel & Wallen, 1990). Therefore, the researcher chose key informants who were subject to interview guide. Furthermore, the researcher used census sampling technique. In this regards, census sampling technique means that the researcher will take all censuses case. The researcher assessed one secondary school, 1 head teacher, and 70 parents. The technique was adopted to acquire a sample from secondary schools in Nyarugenge District.

3.4 Data Collection Instruments

The researcher used open ended questions to make participants free in expressing their opinion. In addition, closed ended questions were used where participants were asked to tick appropriate answers. The questionnaires were distributed to the chosen learners, and teaching staff members. Moreover, the researcher used interview guide. In this regard, an interview guide was adopted to gather qualitative information. In fact, non-numerical information was collected using a conversation between the researcher and the key informants. Interview guide is very pertinent owing to the flexibility, adaptability it offer to different persons (Frankel & Wallen, 1990). This technique was applied to parents and head teachers.

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 The distribution of the respondents and Responses return rate

This study was conducted in one secondary school where the respondents were comprised of 1 school leader, 50 teachers of the secondary school level, 173 students of the secondary advanced levels and 26 parents including the general assembly committee who day to day represent the parents and frequently visit the school to ensure the students and teachers wellbeing. During this study it was observed that all respondents were present to provide data except some parents who missed during the assessments but the number of those who were present was enough to provided adequate needed data.

4.2 Presentation of the findings

The findings were presented, interpreted and discussed in line with their specific objectives which were: “To identify socio-economic status of parents on reduction of dropout rate in secondary schools of Nyarugenge District-Rwanda, to examine the level of students’ dropout rate in secondary schools of Nyarugenge District-Rwanda, to examine the relationship between family socio-economic status and dropout rate in secondary schools of Nyarugenge District-Rwanda”. And the findings were presented as follow:

4.3 Identifying socio-economic status of parents on reduction of dropout

The respondent’s students were asked if they had ever dropped out of school and they responded:

Table 2: Student’s dropout

Statement	Yes		No		Total
	Freq	%	Freq	%	
Students’ dropout	11	6.3	162	93.7	173

Source: Primary source (2022).

During this study, students were asked if they have ever dropped out of school and 6.3% responded yes while 93.7% responded no. Even if the majority of the students answered that they never dropped out of school but some 6.3% responded; yes. This means that in Nyarugenge district some students had ever dropped out but due to intensive and day to day mobilization and inspections by different stakeholders many of the students understood the importance of schooling and decided to come back for learning.

Table 3: The reasons made the students dropout

Some of the reasons	Freq	%
Lack of school materials	2	18
Orphanage	1	9
Family conflicts	5	46
Lack of school fees	1	9
Hanger	1	9
Family poverty	1	9
Total	11	100

Source: Primary source (2022).

Those who agreed that they have ever dropped out were asked the problems made them dropout of the school and the majority 46% responded family conflicts, 18% answered lack of school materials, 9% answered; lack of school fees, 9% answered; orphanage, 9% answered; hanger while 9% answered; family poverty.

Table 4: The parent involvement in students schooling

Some of the reasons	Freq	%
Provision of school materials	157	90.7
Provision school fees	142	82
Transport from home to school	21	12
Total mean	106.7	61.6

Source: Primary source (2022).

As to whether the parents contribute to the students' education for encouraging them attending the school, 90.7% of the respondents answered parents provide school materials, 82% answered parents pay school fees, while 12% answered parents support in ensuring students transport to schools. This showed that students who need transport are so limited due to that the Government of Rwanda through the Ministry of Education provided access to education where the availability of basic education schools reduced the long journey travelled by the students from home to school and vice versa. The respondents have mentioned the others support got from the parents for their effective attending of the schools such as guidance for the schooling, helping in homework.

Table 5: Students views on the family socio-economic status

Statements	Never		Rare		Neutral		S.times		Always		Mean	Sd
	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%		
My family guides and counsels me	12	7	9	5	25	14.5	63	36.4	64	37	.30	.6
My parents/ guardians are educated that's why they care about my studies	8	4.6	2	1.1	20	1.1	86	50	57	33	.15	.38
My family is rich that's why I study effectively	21	12.1	54	31	24	14	42	24	32	18	.16	.41
My parents have good occupation that's why they motivate for better success	16	9	24	14	32	18	56	32	45	26	1.8	.2

Source: Primary source (2022).

The respondents were asked if their family guides and counsels them for positive discipline and 37% answered always, while 36.4% answered sometimes. When asked if their parents/ guardians were educated to care about their studies, 33% answered always, 50% answered sometimes, the we asked if the family was rich to help them study effectively, 18% answered always, 24% answered sometimes, 31% answered rarely, when asked if the parents had good occupations to motivate them learning for success, 26% answered always, 32% answered sometimes. This implies that both students from poor and rich families could drop out of the schools due to some different family issues or peer pressure. It was found that the active family in the student's education played a big role in the children education. Not only providing food but motivating children through guidance and counseling can also reduce dropout rate in secondary schools.

Cardoso and Verner (2007) conducted a study in Brazil and the findings revealed that poverty as the most common secondary contributory factor for students' school dropout. All low income countries have one trait in common; they ration their education according to social stratification, where children from rich homes attain the best schools while students from poor home attain the worst school. In most poor countries of Africa less than half of all children ever get to schools.

Table 6: Teachers views on the students' dropout rate in secondary schools

Statements	Never		Rare		Neutral		S.times		Always		Mean	Sd
	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%		
Most of my students fail to attend classes because they are from 1 st category (low income category)	4	8	2	4	7	14	21	42	16	32	.3	.5
My students dropout due to that their parents/ guardians do not have job	0	0	4	8	11	22	25	50	10	20	1.2	.6
Some of my students do not attended class regularly due to that their families are from low income family	7	14	2	4	3	6	33	66	6	12	2.1	1.5
My students drop out of school because the parents lack of occupation	2	4	5	10	1	2	24	48	18	36	3.2	.8

Source: Primary source (2022).

The teachers' respondents were asked if students fail to attend classes because they are from 1st category (low income category) and only 32% answered always, while 42% answered sometimes. When asked if students dropout due to that their parents/ guardians do not have job, 20% answered always, 50% answered sometimes, they were asked some their students do not attended class regularly due to that they were from low income family, 12% answered always, 66% answered sometimes, 14% answered never, when asked students drop out of school because the parents lack of occupation 36% answered always, 48% answered sometimes. This implies that both students from low income families were likely to dropout due to lack of basic needs and assistance from their family members.

During an interview with head teachers and parents of the selected secondary school, the teachers and parents were asked how they considered the contribution of family socio-economic status to students' dropout and responded that most of the students in Nyarugenge district dropout due to the family conflicts, peer children who have dropped out, lack of basic needs and basic materials for schooling. They kept arguing that some of the families do not care about their children education which result to the poor performance and end up in dropping out fearing to repeat in the same class. Others parents claimed that they fail to pay for the school fees (incentives for teachers) and children prefer to indulge themselves into small business and they forget attending school. Other students indulge themselves in drugs and end up becoming addicted. Parental control becomes limited when children reach to teenager stage and they start becoming independent and follow bad groups which lead them to leave the school. Even though children were accused to leave the school without clear reasons, parents claimed that lack of positive discipline plays a role in students' dropout.

4.4 Examining the level of students' dropout rate in secondary schools

The researcher has described the findings in line with the second objective which was to examine the level of dropout rate in secondary schools of Nyarugenge District.

Table 7: Students views on dropout rate in secondary schools

Statements	Never		Rare		Neutral		S.times		Always		Mean	Sd
	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%		
I have ever dropped out school because of my family low income	14	8	26	15	7	4.1	96	55	30	17	.9	.11
I have ever dropped out school because I am not motivated by my parents	2	1.1	24	14	9	5.2	78	45	60	34.6	1.0	.81
My colleagues dropped out due to their family poverty	5	2.9	12	7	5	2.9	74	43	77	44.5	1.2	.2
I left the school for long because teachers are absent	9	5.2	102	59	43	24.8	5	2.9	14	9	.8	.32
My school teachers and head teacher are lesser-faire that's why some students drop out	42	24	37	21	46	26	21	12	27	15.6	.12	.01

Source: Primary source (2022).

The students were asked if they have ever dropped out school because of my family low income, and 17% answered always, while 55% answered sometimes. When asked if they have ever dropped out school because they were not motivated by my parents, 34.6% answered always, 45% answered sometimes, they were asked if some of their colleagues dropped out due to their family poverty, 44.5% answered always, 43.5% answered sometimes, 14% answered never, when asked If they left the school for long because teachers are absent, 9% answered always, 2.9% answered sometimes while the majority 59% answered rare. They were asked if their school teachers and head teacher are lesser-faire that some students drop out, 24% answered never and 21% answered rare, while 24% answered never and 21% answered rare. This implies that students drop out due to the family and societal issues than school problems and threat. Nkoma (2009) revealed that children who played truant or dropped out from schools belonged not only to economically poor families but also to the parents with little formal education.

Table 8: Teachers views on students' dropout rate in secondary schools

Statements	Never		Rare		Neutral		S.times		Always		Mean	Sd
	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%		
In my class some students have dropped out due to lack of school materials	8	16	19	38	7	14	9	18	7	14	1.2	1.1
In my class some students have dropped out due to lack of family possibility	1	2	3	6	8	16	26	52	12	24	1.9	1.0
Many students who drop out of my class are from category 1 and 2 (poor)	6	12	14	28	11	22	12	24	7	14	2.0	.9
My students dropout due lack of guidance and counseling	2	4	2	4	5	10	32	64	9	18	1.1	.3

Source: Primary source (2022).

The researcher described the teachers' responses on the on dropout rate in secondary schools. The respondents were asked if students have dropped out due to lack of school materials, and 14% answered always, 18% answered sometimes while the majority 38% answered rare. When asked if students have dropped out due to lack of family possibility, 24% answered always, 52% answered sometimes. Teachers were asked if their students who drop out were belonging to the category 1 and 2 (poor), 14% answered always, 24% answered sometimes, while 28% answered rare. They were asked if students' dropout due lack of guidance and counseling 18% answered always, 64% answered sometimes. This shows that that students drop out due to lack of family responsibilities.

During an interview with the parents and head teacher, the respondents were asked about the parents/ head teachers/ guardians responsibilities to combat dropout in schools and replied: Parents are the backbone to the education of dropout in terms of acting like front liners in education trough sending children to schools, providing them with school materials, provision of guidance and counseling, ensuring parental control and communication with the school, allowing their children with enough time to revise their studies, paying school fees and other school contributions, participating in the meeting and other general assembly meeting organized by the school, raising their awareness and strengthening dialogue to drag abuse and sexual education.

4.5 Examining the relationship between family socio-economic status and dropout

The researcher described the results related to the relationship between family socio-economic status and dropout rate in secondary schools of Nyarugenge District.

Table 9: the relationship between family socio-economic status and dropout rate in secondary schools

Correlations

Variables		Dropout rate in secondary schools	Family socio-economic status
Dropout rate in secondary schools	Spearman correlation	1	-.2
	Significance. (2-tailed)		.01
	N	173	173
Family socio-economic status	Spearman correlation	-.2	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.01	
	N	173	173

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The researcher describes the relationship between family socio-economic status and dropout rate in secondary schools. The results showed that the P-value was .01. While the Spearman correlation was -.2. This means that family socio-economic status negatively affects the dropout rate in secondary schools. This was shown by the results because when the

Spearman's coefficient correlation lies between -1 and +1 to show negative correction or positive correlation. Thus, it was interpreted that family socio-economic status contribute to the students' dropout at low extent because the big number of students who dropped out were not only from the poor family but some of them were from the families with possibilities.

Table 10: Regression analysis on family socio-economic status and dropout rate Linear regression

Regression statistics	
R	.643
R Square	.401
Adjust R Square	.046
Standard Error	.045
Total Number of cases	134

Regression analysis

As to whether there was a relationship between the two variables, the researcher used regression analysis where showed that R square was .401, R was .643 and standard error was .045 which shows that the family socio-economic status contribute to the reduction of dropout at 40%. This study showed that the parents and the community play a big role in the reduction of dropout even though the children from families with low capacity were not only ones to dropout but also the students with rich families did.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 conclusions

It was concluded that family living conditions have an influence to children effective learning. As confirmed by the parents, teachers, students and the school leader, students from families with possibility to support their children with school materials school fees, and regular guidance and counseling, they follow their studies without any harm and the performance become successful.

The dropout rate in Nyarugenge district was very low depending on the intensive mobilizations and campaigns done by the stakeholders of education. Even though the numbers of students who dropout is very low children do not attend class regularly due to that they have many distractions and others, as the results had shown, they don't get enough time to interact with their parents for positive discipline.

For the relationship, the result showed that the family social economic status plays a big role in the reduction of increase of the dropout out rate. The respondents confirmed that when parents and the entire society actively participate in the activities of reducing dropout, they succeed due to that some students leave the schools because their family are not able to satisfy their learning needs.

5.2 Recommendations for further studies

The overall goal of this research was attained and the information got was clear, analyzed and concluded. After analyzing information, researcher came up with the following recommendations:

After identifying some weakness among the parents who fail to ensure their responsibilities, the researcher has recommended that the City of Kigali should strengthen parental mobilization to the involvement in children education.

Nyarugenge district should grant much training on both students and parents on the causes and consequences of school dropout.

The educational officials should conduct regular inspections in schools and communities to ensure all children attend schools. Educational officials and local leaders to ensure working in collaboration with the chief villages in the identification of families living in conflicts and the children who do not attend schools appropriately.

The schools should closely work with children, teachers and parents to ensure all children from low income families and rich families attend class regularly and communicate to the school leadership immediately when a student develop an unusual behaviors which can lead them to dropout rate.

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